

A master-slave hybrid position/force control for robot-aided pedicle tapping

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Abstract—This paper presents a master-slave hybrid position/force control designed to enhance screw placement accuracy and reduce surgery duration in robot-aided spinal fixation, while simultaneously ensuring surgeon’s comfort. The proposed approach allows the surgeon to switch control modes based on bone layers and his/her preferences. Experimental results with non-expert users threading a spine phantom demonstrate an optimal trade-off between placement accuracy (error concerning the desired end position: 0.02 ± 0.03 [mm]), surgery duration (task completion time: 11.8 ± 2.6 [s]), and perceived workload.

Index Terms—Hybrid position/force control, Surgical robotics, Spinal surgery, Pedicle screw fixation

I. INTRODUCTION

Pedicle screw fixation is a complex spinal surgery that requires accurate screw placement to prevent neurological injury or bone fractures. While robotic systems have enhanced screw placement accuracy compared to traditional free-hand techniques, the tasks of drilling and tapping the screw path are still performed manually by the surgeon. This reliance on surgeon expertise introduces variability in the surgical outcomes and increases physical strain for the surgeon [1].

Autonomous systems, while promising, lack adaptability in unexpected situations and are not widely accepted by surgeons [2]. In contrast, semi-autonomous systems offer a balance between comfort and lack of direct control. However, they still depend on the surgeon’s sensory-motor coordination and reactivity to reach the optimal screw depth. Hence, it is crucial to develop a control strategy that eliminates this dependency while simultaneously reducing the duration of the procedure, as this would lead to improved surgical outcomes and reduced risk of complications.

Therefore, starting from the promising results of the authors’ previous work [2] and the related patent [4], this work introduces a hybrid position/force semi-autonomous control strategy that enables the surgeon to switch control modes depending on the bone layer, with the aim of: i) enhancing screw placement accuracy, and ii) reducing operative time.

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The surgical scenario, involving the use of the proposed control strategy for pedicle tapping, is illustrated in Fig. 1a. During placement, the screw must follow the path represented by the green arrow in Fig. 1b. For the outer cortical (L1) and cancellous (L2) layers, two Control Modes (CM), named CM1 – pushing mode and CM2 – torque mode, are available. These modes enable fine adjustment of the robot speed and offer direct control over the interaction forces/torques between the surgical tool and the patient. For the critical inner cortical layer (L3), where accuracy is crucial to avoid nerve and vessel injury, a master-slave Position Error-Based (PEB) control, called CM3 - PEB mode, is introduced.

The proposed strategy was implemented on a robotic system consisting of a 7-degree-of-freedom robotic arm and a dedicated master-slave module, attached to the robot end-effector. Non-expert users were recruited to perform tapping operations on an anthropomorphic spine phantom.

II. THE PROPOSED CONTROL STRATEGY

A block diagram of the proposed master-slave hybrid position/force control for pedicle tapping is shown in Fig. 2. The surgeon, based on visual feedback from a vision system, identifies the current bone layer and selects the appropriate control mode (CM1 or CM2 for L1 and L2 layers, and CM3 for L3 layer). The three control modes are implemented through a force control loop which acts in parallel to a position control loop. The former allows the surgeon to finely control interaction forces/torques between the patient and the surgical tool while the latter restricts the orientation of the surgical tool to align it with the pre-planned tapping axis. In the following, details about the position and force control loops are provided.

A. Position loop

The position control loop receives as input the desired and the measured pose of the tapping axis. The output consists of a position stabilizing action y_p , which can be derived from a conventional inverse dynamics control, as presented in the

Fig. 1. a) Surgical scenario with the proposed control strategy, b) Correct screw path and the relation between control modes and bone layers.

authors' previous work [3]. This action includes proportional and derivative components that manage position error concerning the desired pose of the surgical instrument, thereby providing mechanical guidance to the surgeon during tapping and allowing him/her to manually move the robot end-effector along the tapping axis, by means of a hands-on approach. In particular, y_p is expressed as follows

$$y_p = J^\dagger(q) [Ad^{-1} (K_P Ad \tilde{x} - K_D Ad \dot{\tilde{x}})] \quad (1)$$

where $J^\dagger(q)$ is the right pseudo-inverse of the robot geometric Jacobian, Ad is an adjoint matrix for base-to-end-effector frame transformation, K_P and K_D are 6x6 matrices for proportional and derivative gains (set to 0 in the tapping direction), and \tilde{x} is the pose error in the base frame. More details about these terms can be found in [3].

B. Force loop

The force control loop varies depending on the specific control mode. In *CM1 mode*, the surgeon applies a force along the tapping axis. The force detected at the haptic handle F_m^t and the torque exerted by the surgical tool τ_m^t serve as inputs to the force control loop, which outputs the tool control action τ_c^t . This action, as described in previous work [3], results in the surgical instrument applying a torque proportional to the force exerted by the surgeon, and is expressed as follows: $\tau_c^t = K_c(k \cdot F_m^t - \tau_m^t)$. In *CM2 mode*, the surgeon applies a torque around the tapping axis. The torque measured at the haptic handle, denoted as τ_m^h , and τ_m^t serve as inputs to the force control loop, which generates τ_c^t . This action, also described in previous work [3], results in the surgical instrument applying a torque proportional to the torque exerted by the surgeon, and is defined as follows: $\tau_c^t = K_c(k \cdot \tau_m^h - \tau_m^t)$. Moreover, in *CM2*, the force control loop, through a force stabilizing action y_F , allows the robot to exert a thrust force along the tapping axis proportional to the measured torque τ_m^h . In particular, y_F is expressed as follows

$$y_F = J^\dagger(q) [Ad^{-1} K_F F_R] \quad (2)$$

where K_F is a 6x6 matrix defining force action gains (non-zero only along the tapping axis), while $F_R = k \tau_m^h$ is a 6x1 vector specifying the desired robot thrust force. This action is not present in *CM1*, where the surgeon directly applies the force along the tapping axis. Finally, in *CM3 - PEB mode*, the surgeon rotates the handle around the tapping axis, which causes a variation in the position of the haptic handle p_m . Simultaneously, both the position and velocity of the surgical instrument, p_s and ω_s respectively, are measured. Thus, the tool control action is given by: $\tau_c^t = K_P(p_m - p_s) - K_D \cdot \omega_s$.

Fig. 2. Overview of the proposed control strategy.

Fig. 3. Experimental setup.

TABLE I
EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Target Position Error (TPE)	0.02 ± 0.03 [mm]
Task Completion Time (TCT)	11.8 ± 2.6 [s]
maximum Deviation from the Tapping Axis (DTA)	0.016 ± 0.005 [rad]
Rapid Upper Limb Assessment tool (RULA)	2.4 ± 0.7
NASA Task Load Index (NASA-TLX)	42.2 ± 13.7

This guarantees that the tool applies a torque proportional to the position error between master and slave. The force control loop again contributes to the robot thrust force through y_F .

III. EXPERIMENTAL VALIDATION

The experimental setup used to evaluate the proposed control strategy, depicted in Fig. 3, consists of a customized configuration with key components including a robotic arm (KUKA LWR 4+), a handle functioning as the master device, and a surgical instrument acting as the slave. Both the master and slave components are equipped with MAXON motors. Eleven participants, equipped with IMUs, performed a tapping task on an anthropomorphic spine phantom, aiming to reach a pre-defined end position (blue line in Fig. 1b), visualized through a Graphical User Interface (GUI). The performance metrics, summarized in Tab. I, assessed procedure accuracy based on both the positional error relative to the target end position and the orientation deviation from the desired tapping axis pose. Additionally, efficiency was evaluated by the time required to complete the surgical procedure. A biomechanical analysis was conducted using the RULA tool, while perceived workload was assessed through the NASA-TLX questionnaire.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The results demonstrated the strong capability of the proposed strategy to ensure an optimal trade-off across all evaluated aspects. It achieved high levels of procedure effectiveness and efficiency, allowed the surgeon to maintain comfortable postures, and minimized perceived workload. Future research will focus on involving surgeons as participants to more accurately evaluate the acceptability and practical applicability of the proposed method within the medical community.

REFERENCES

- [1] Hsiao, Chih-Kun et al. "Forearm muscular strength and performance fatigability in orthopaedic surgeons when performing bone screw fixations." Applied ergonomics vol. 87 (2020): 103135.
- [2] Moustiris, G P et al. "Evolution of autonomous and semi-autonomous robotic surgical systems: a review of the literature." The international journal of medical robotics + computer assisted surgery: MRCAS vol. 7,4 (2011): 375-92. doi:10.1002/rcs.408
- [3] Morfino, R et al. "A hybrid position/force control for robot-aided pedicle tapping in spinal surgery." IEEE RAS EMBS 10th International Conference on Biomedical Robotics and Biomechatronics (BioRob 2024).
- [4] Lauretti, C et al. (2021). Apparato e metodo di controllo di un manipolatore robotico PATENT N. IT2020000019 00A1 granted in Italy on January 27, 2023. PCT application n. WO2021152556A1